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Transparency in Case Studies: Methodological Appendices

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When writing qualitative case study research, most of us find that the very stuff of analysis—that is, the qualitative data—is lengthy and nuanced. Additionally, qualitative methods are often used in situations where “theories are underdeveloped and concepts are vague” (Ragin, Berg-Schlosser, and de Meur 1998, 750). To be robust and compelling, the data we use may require lengthy explanation, precisely because we wish to capture complexity. Overall, qualitative research relies on words—often lots of them—to get our point across.

Moreover, induction is often key to the sorts of insights that qualitative researchers are poised to offer (Bendassolli 2013). We gather data to form new hypotheses and explanations—a process that can be crucial to “gain[ing] inferential leverage over different questions” (Yom 2015, 618). However, inductive reasoning requires moving from observed data to abstract concepts in ways that cannot be fully deduced from initial premises or hypotheses (Bendassolli 2013, 2). Therefore, the transparency goal of clearly “linking evidence to inference” (Bennett, Fairfield, and Soifer 2019, 2) can be particularly challenging to achieve. Forming propositions or generalizations in qualitative research will often involve choosing one interpretation over others when it comes to data and to the vaguer aspects of the theories and concepts with which we are engaging. The fact that qualitative researchers often make these sorts of choices leaves space for particular kinds of questions to emerge on the reader’s part about how we have arrived at our conclusions.

This contribution focuses on how my coauthors, Sara Casella Colombeau and Elisabeth Badenhoop, and I used a particular tool—a methodological appendix—to explicitly address some of the concerns that qualitative data and the inductive process in general can raise in the more constrained space of an article-length text. The research and appendix were recently published in *Comparative Political Studies* (Slaven, Casella Colombeau, and Badenhoop 2021). A methodological appendix can be defined simply as supplementary (in this case, online-only) material that provides greater detail and specification of the methodological approach than the traditional format of a qualitative research article would allow. We created the methodological appendix thanks to the encouragement and suggestions from others (see below). In conveying our positive experience here, we hope to inspire others to consider it as an arrow in one’s quiver for bolstering transparency in qualitative research.

The Project

We arrived at creating a methodological appendix for this article relatively late in the process of writing the article (and in retrospect, perhaps a little later than ideal, as discussed below). Indeed, it is important to situate writing a methodological appendix as only part of the longer work process of bringing an article to publication.

The three of us had worked on a comparative project that was fully centered on gathering and analyzing qualitative process-tracing data about policy deliberations surrounding immigration policy. The data were collected through a combination of archival research and elite interviews, which we performed

across three countries (Germany, France, and the United Kingdom). In performing a qualitative three-country comparison, we knew we would have to be extremely concise and economical with the process-tracing data we would present. The article would require intensive co-writing and editing. We also agreed, after substantial conceptual discussion, that our analysis would be most robust if we used our data to examine four distinct theoretical accounts drawn from previous literature; this therefore became a four-by-three (so to speak) qualitative, comparative, process-tracing article.

Because the theoretical accounts we were examining were not fully systematized into theories with already-elaborated sets of observable implications that could be tested deductively, we employed a “theory-building” process-tracing approach. As one example, to test whether the linking of immigration and welfare policy was driven by welfare-retrenchment logics, we had to draw from existing literature to identify what sorts of evidence would show us it was in fact this logic that was dominant in the process and not another one, since this had not been extensively specified in existing theorization. Such an approach “starts with empirical material and uses a structured analysis of this material to detect a plausible hypothetical causal mechanism”; while in this approach “existing theorization is... used to inspire us in collecting evidence,” nonetheless it is “at heart an inductive exercise” (Beach and Pedersen 2013, 60).

Beyond the number of cases and accounts examined, the need to build a single authorial voice from data in three different languages, with all of us (as early career researchers) taking up posts in new locations during the writing process, meant that completing and submitting what would become the “main article” felt like its own milestone. Given the effort it had taken to get to that point, we were eager to start receiving reviews and did not initially contemplate the inclusion of extensive supplementary material.

Writing the Methodological Appendix

The suggestion that we add a methodological appendix emerged from the review process. It was part of how the editors suggested we respond to a cluster of questions reviewers had raised around inductive aspects of our analysis within our research design: specifically, how we determined what would provide evidence for the theoretical propositions we were considering. The theoretical accounts we were examining were not ones previously developed enough such that they came ready with likely empirical indicators to employ deductively in our research. Therefore, in our research design we inductively inferred what would evidence them. The

reviewers accordingly asked for more detail on: how we identified potential empirical “indicators” of these theoretical accounts; our reasoning that interviews with the kinds of policymakers that we focused on sampling would produce this evidence; the specific kind of process-tracing approach we employed; and how we consulted documents as part of triangulating interview data. We were grateful for this feedback and pleased that our article had been received positively on the whole—and though we had focused on developing many of these points to the extent possible within space constraints, we saw that we had quite a lot of specifying to do to address those reviewer requests.

At this point, we resolved to write an appendix to submit with our revisions to the article. Rather than immediately setting about writing a longer and more detailed treatment of our methodology, we first discussed this feedback in order to land on what specific purposes the appendix should serve. The main objectives that we identified for this appendix were to lay out how and why we developed inductive inferences about what evidence would support, fail to support, or refute various theoretical accounts. We did this by referring to existing literature, which suggested these inferences were reasonable. We also sought to make clear our argument for why our approach comprised a robust analysis. While it may be self-evident, it could bear emphasis that including an appendix was not merely a way of getting around article word limits (although the reason it was suggested in the first place was precisely because all of this information could not be accommodated in a qualitative, three-case article of a reasonable length). In addition, it served as a space where—building upon the explication of important points in the article—we could enhance the transparency of our inductive approach in specific and strategic ways related to the particular methodology upon which we relied.

To achieve these analytic ends, we settled on an appendix that would include the following sequence of sections:

Methodological framework. First, we decided to specify the particular model of process-tracing we were adopting for our analysis (along with our operative notion of “causal mechanisms”) and explain why this approach required the researcher to make inductive inferences. This section specifies how induction operates in this sort of research design, why it is a naturally appropriate approach for answering our sort of research question, and what would constitute robust induction in this model. This is the part that deals with what would be most strictly called “methodology.”

Establishing the case for our inferences. Second, we sought to explain that the specific inductive inferences we made as part of this methodology were founded upon a robust reading of previous scholarship. This section built on discussions that had been in the literature review of the submitted article, but it aimed to address the questions that reviewers had raised in a more fully systematic way. Our inferences concerned what sorts of empirical evidence might support (or fail to support) previous theoretical accounts of the policy reasoning underlying the process we were examining. We specified four categories of indicators and what we would expect to see empirically as evidence of each account in terms of each category of indicator. Where the main article focused on and highlighted those indicators that ended up being most analytically relevant to our cases, the appendix also identified how we considered some that turned out to be less specifically relevant.

Explaining our methods and their suitability. Third, we wanted to explain how our decisions about data collection and sampling suited the above and would produce the kind of data the analysis required (or perhaps an analytically useful absence of evidence). Here, we laid out in greater detail how we set about gathering our data and then analyzed it in ways that facilitated cross-case comparison. At the same time, certain aspects of our research design, like our selection of national cases, did not attract any questions from the reviewers, and we decided that these did not bear specific further discussion, as the reasoning behind the logic of case selection already appeared sufficiently transparent to our audience.

The process of conceptualizing and developing this appendix was concurrent with—and interrelated to—working on the main article. Rather than creating a standalone document providing further explanation, working on the appendix meant working on both documents and making sure both reflected and reinforced each other.

Benefits and Challenges

Our methodological appendix was well received by reviewers—which, of course, probably biases the following assessment. Nonetheless, for the purposes of those considering methodology appendices as a tool for increasing research transparency, it is worth laying out rather systematically: What were the downsides of doing this? What were the upsides?

In terms of downsides, the most notable is likely to be the amount of time it can take to write a methodological appendix thoroughly and the effect this can have upon (re)submission timeframes. Our methodological appendix ended up at nearly 6,000 words—close to half the length of the main article. It can be easy to underestimate how much time it will take to compile (in conjunction, of course, with revisions on the main article). In our case, transparently explaining our inductive inferences meant a deeper dive into literatures related both to methodology and methods per se, as well as general theory surrounding the topic of our analysis. Work related to writing the methodological appendix probably corresponded to about two extra months before we could resubmit the article. What we had expected to do in three months, in other words, took us about five. Of course, in principle, much of this kind of work could be done before submission, with revisions occurring after the review. While it stands to reason that writing the appendix before submission may take somewhat less time, it is still likely to be considerable.

Compared to those costs, the upsides for us were far greater in both advancing the analysis and making it more transparent. First, we found that engaging in the writing of this appendix did meaningfully sharpen our analysis, even in our own minds, and improved the main article as well as the overall package. In particular, the process of differentiating which sorts of inductive inferences ended up performing an important analytical function (thus bearing focus in the main article)—and which were important to have considered but did not end up playing such a role (thus meriting discussion primarily in the appendix)—enhanced our own mental maps of the analysis. This benefit on the author's side, of course, translated over to readers (or, at least, to the small sample of them who instrumentally matter most). The reviewers responded that they found it more straightforward to follow all of the significant moves the article made, and that including the appendix made transparent a number of aspects of the analysis which had at first seemed somewhat murky or more tenuous. To that point, the drafting of the appendix played (in our minds) an important part in the review process, because it was a highly legible signal of how much we had valued the feedback we received and how seriously we had taken it. While, of course, that is not sufficient for a positive peer-review outcome, it is usually necessary.

The most notable upside to writing this methodological appendix, however, is one that we did not quite expect: It has strengthened reader engagement with the research. Somewhat surprisingly to us, people have actually read the appendix. Of course, an appendix will not be read by nearly as many people as the number

who will consult an article, and the metrics on our article certainly reflect this. Supplementary material will never get the casual clicks that an article may attract. (And, of course, any reader who still relies on a print copy of the journal will not see it.) However, for readers who are engaging with an article's arguments or topic on a more detailed level, a methodological appendix can strengthen this engagement. The transparency it advances can underscore the robustness of research and (hopefully) its merit as a possible future reference point. Since our article was first published online, people have reached out to us as much about its methodology, appendix, and transparency aspects—with overwhelmingly positive feedback—as much as they have about any other aspect of the work. We have been surprised—very pleasantly—by this.

Given these upsides and downsides, is a methodological appendix worth doing? In our case, it definitely was. The principal cost, the extra time it took to create it, was clearly worth it in order to bolster the transparency of our analysis in ways that resonated with our intended audience.

Suggested Practices

Just as importantly, given this experience, are there any recommendations we can convey? And is there anything that in retrospect we would have done differently?

First, it is worth considering when a methodological appendix may have benefits compared to other transparency measures, such as Annotating for Transparent Inquiry (ATI), which also can offer readers more information about the researcher's choices in analyzing data. Unlike annotations, methodological appendices provide the opportunity to explain analytical choices in a single document that can start by establishing a general approach and then explain in greater detail how it was operationalized. Therefore, compared to ATI, an appendix may be beneficial when the researcher's challenge is to substantiate an approach to interpretation or induction, rather than explain how particular pieces of data have been analyzed. By allowing researchers to address overarching interpretive issues in relation to each other within a single document, an appendix may have advantages in supporting research transparency by deepening the reader's overall view of how an analytical approach ties together.

To this point, from our experience, a main recommendation for those choosing to write such an appendix as a way of advancing the transparency of how you “linked evidence to inference” is to start writing it with a good idea of just what sorts of questions the appendix would need to address for that purpose. This may sound somewhat self-evident, but just as all of the

other “sections” of a scholarly article serve some sort of isomorphic function while performing a particular role in advancing a distinct and original argument, so too should a methodological appendix. It should have, if not an “argument” per se, a sense of purpose, and one which is molded around the argument of the article as a whole and the particular moves in the analysis which additional discussion would ground or enhance. If inductive reasoning is required by a methodology or research design, a methodological appendix is a very suitable place to engage in the kind of extended discussion that explains why it is robust. Without this purpose-driven approach, an appendix could run the risk of being more of a repository of relevant information that did not make the initial cut due to space limitations.

When in the writing process does it make sense to write such an appendix? We had a discussion about this and about how much, in retrospect, we might have done ahead of time. We can see both sides of this argument, and based on our experience, would advise a sort of middle path—though this will, of course, depend on one's individual situation. On the one hand, writing this appendix earlier may have saved us some time and questions later. On the other hand, if the purpose of an appendix is to clarify analysis for readers, it can sometimes be hard to anticipate issues that will arise when it is subjected to the (ideally) deep reading of review. If an appendix ought to have a purpose, it may be possible in great part to know what this is pre-review, but new—or more urgent—objectives nonetheless may emerge in the review process. Considering this and the time it can take to write such an appendix, there will often be a reasonable argument for waiting to write one until after a revise and resubmit decision. In general, we definitely recommend keeping strong accounting of these inductive inferences in a table or other visualization which describes and relates them to various concepts or theories being employed or tested. This can be helpful in drafting an analysis and can serve as the foundation for more extensive elaboration in an appendix. One of the most worthwhile things we did as part of our article was to compile a table that we ended up including in our methodological appendix, which lays out for readers (as well as ourselves) how we identified data that may indicate the policymaking logics we were examining within our cases.

Beyond this, we would recommend—during the research and writing process—flagging and explicitly gathering material for later organization in a possible appendix. One thing to keep in mind here is that the line between “methodology” and “theory” can be quite thin, especially if a researcher's methodology requires inductive inferences to be made based upon previous

theoretical discussion in the field. In this sense, keeping track of references, points, or issues which may not end up playing a main analytical role—but which may be important to include as part of “showing your work”—would be advisable. A methodological appendix is only one possible tool in advancing qualitative research

transparency and will not always make sense. But in our experience, it does make sense to keep it in mind from the start as a potentially worthwhile endeavor which you may end up deciding to do—and to accordingly make some basic preparations.

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